

Generative AI-Powered Travel Mobile Applications: Improving Tourist Customized Experience Using Large Language Models

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is a multifaceted activity that utilizes historical and artistic capacities, both natural and man-made, to create a pleasurable experience. Information technology can improve the quality of tourism services. Travel mobile applications, serving as a tourist's companion on every journey, are among the best examples of information technology's use in the tourism industry. We used the documentary method as the research methodology in this study. At first, we model easy traveling through an integrated mobile app. Then, we show how large language models as the knowledge repository of artificial intelligence have been developed during the past ten years. Also, we explain how these language models can provide benefits to the tourist through the mobile applications and how the tourist, as the application user, can make the journey a more enjoyable experience. Finally, we develop a new model that supports the development of an inclusive scenario for fellow travelers. This model is an innovative idea and can create a huge technical transformation in the tourism industry and a big turnover in tourism finance.

Keywords: Tourism, Travel Mobile Applications, Artificial Intelligence, Large Language Models, Tourist, User Experience

Travel Mobile Applications: Reconceptualizing the Tourism Industry

Tourism is one of the best examples of changing the concept of industry in the mentality of people. Historically, the word industry refers to working with tools. The traditional concept of industry has favored the physical labor of unskilled workers even more than the intellectual activity of expert human beings. However, the process of industrialization of human societies removed the industry concept from its instrumental and physical meaning. In the new semantic context, any business that can facilitate the process of automation is accepted as a part of the industry. Accordingly, the intellectual and mental activities of specialists have found a more important role in industries. Tourism as a multifaceted activity that utilizes historical and artistic capacities, both natural and man-made, to create a pleasurable experience is a successful example of industry in the modern sense.

Compared to other industries, the tourism industry has more ability and talent to use information technology [8]. From the author's point of view, information technology is mainly focused on the soft sector of the industry, and its products are mostly intangible. Tourism has essential unity with information technology. Both of these areas have been developed with the aim of making life simple and enjoyable. For this reason, the integration of information technology and tourism happened much faster than the penetration of information technology in a field such as fisheries. On one hand, the embrace of tourism has always been open to technology, and on the other hand, technology has made maximum use of the unique capacity of tourism to create and implement the best ideas.

Travel is the central concept of tourism [4]. Here, we do not use the concept of travel in its broad sense. Travel in the most general sense refers to the movement of people with various purposes. We do not refer to the transfer of a student from home to school, the transfer of a worker from a factory to home, the transfer of a retiree to meet his/her friends, and other similar examples that we see or personally experience in our daily lives. Of course, the central idea of this paper can support any journey and any experience of displacement. However, we only focus on the enjoyable experience of traveling to another city or country to visit a historical building, stay in nature, enjoy national dishes, or buy artistic handicrafts.

One of the best examples of the use of information technology in the tourism industry are mobile applications that play the role of a tourist's companion in every journey [7]. In recent years, an increasing number of these applications have been developed to support tourists. Successful applications include *Airbnb* and

HotelTonight. Our goal is not to review the turnover of mobile applications in the tourism industry. However, estimates show that more than sixty percent of tourists use mobile applications [6]. This consumer behavior is becoming a constant habit of every tourist because a successful and enjoyable journey depends on careful planning. Applications allow tourists to control travel schedules, means of transportation, accommodation, and travel costs. Figure 1 illustrates travel management using an integrated mobile application.

Figure 1-Travel Management Using An Integrated Mobile App

Enriching Mobile Applications with Generative Artificial Intelligence: Crossing the Border of Semantics

Artificial intelligence (AI) has a history of more than half a century. However, in less than two years, the public's perception of its impact has changed. Before November 2022, AI was considered a very computational complex field that only a few smart *Computer Science* professionals could understand its scope and apply its function. Artificial intelligence applications that were mainly developed for mobile phones in the last ten years had a role of fantasy and luxury, and non-expert users utilized them mostly for the purposes of entertainment and emotional experience.

However, with the development of the fourth version of GPT and the possibility of real-time dialogue between human and artificial intelligence, the user community experienced an amazing level up. In fact, the exponential growth of artificial intelligence finally made the phase change a reality and created a new paradigm in which AI has become a strong assistant to humans in every field and even performs some tasks better than humans.

The success of artificial intelligence is the result of improving the level of understanding of language. It seems that artificial intelligence, like a human who has learned the language and the locks of his/her communication with the environment have been opened, can now understand humans well and make wishes or commands easily understood by humans. Imagine a child who is unable to speak until the age of three and then begins to speak. S/he gradually learns new words and their usage. A child usually needs four years (3 to 7) to manage successful daily communication. In order to understand how artificial intelligence went through this process, you should consider the three years from 1960s, the beginning of the artificial intelligence life, to 2014, when chatbots (such as Apple Siri, Google Assistant, and Microsoft Cortana) began to emerge in large numbers [1, 9]. The eight-year period from 2014 to November 2022 was the same as the four-year period of artificial intelligence's preliminary mastery of language. It has been almost two years now that AI has passed the preliminary phase of mastering the language and is enriching its language reserve like a teenager who is rapidly developing his/her verbal skills. Figure 2 illustrates how artificial intelligence developed as a language tool.

Figure 2-Development of AI as a Language Tool

Humans use language well because, firstly, they have a rich reservoir of words, and secondly, the brain learns in its decades-long learning process how to put words together in different ways and create various chains of the meaning. The brain learns that each word can have more than one meaning, and words can be put together in different ways. Statistically, the behavior of artificial intelligence, which imitates the behavior of human intelligence, can be explained with the concept of *Factorial* (Equation 1). A factorial is used in statistics to calculate the number of possible combinations and permutations of a set of objects [2]. Thus, we experience a diverse range of hundreds, and even thousands, of different modes in which words can be juxtaposed to produce distinct and unique meanings.

$$n! = n \times (n - 1) \times \dots \times 1 \quad (1)$$

Each form of putting words together creates a particular texture or style of conveying meaning. In the field of artificial intelligence, we simply call this texture a *Model*. Linguistic models are actually textures, styles, or methods for using language words, generating a text, creating a meaning, and conveying a message.

Until 2014, when digital gadgets added chatbots to their features, artificial intelligence lacked an efficient language model. The eight-year period from 2014 to November 2022 has been the time for language models to mature and become generative. Now we have access to mature models that are growing exponentially every day. For this reason, we call new language models *Large Language Models (LLMs)*. LLMs can easily model thousands of words. That is, they can generate creative combinations of the language words to generate new texts and make meanings that have never existed before [3, 5], thus introducing amazing messages into the human communication chain..

Large language models can be fed to any system as input. It means that these models can be injected into the knowledge base of a mobile application, or an application can access the knowledge base of an AI agent that contains the same models. Market popular mobile applications, process the data, and provide the work agenda based on predefined conditions. For example, a mobile taxi application receives the passenger's request, identifies the origin and destination, suggests the agenda to the available agents, and finally connects an agent to the passenger. In such an application, accessible data includes location data, best travel route, and service price. Based on some personal preferences, including the service price, the agent agrees to take the passenger from point A to point B by the best proposed route. In this example, the volume and variety of data at the customer and agent level is limited. However, the same method of processing data and making decisions on the scale of big data, i.e., the taxi company, is also valid. Therefore, on a macro scale, we are facing big companies in the market that process billions of data daily and provide the best possible offer to customers. Theoretically, it can be assumed that the knowledge base of a mobile application can include LLMs in addition to trillions of data points about customers, agents, and products/services. Based on this assumption, a generative AI-powered mobile application is able to level up and cross the border of semantics. That is, it can be expected that a mobile application has access not only to the data extracted from the user query but also to a rich warehouse of words and language models and can execute a parallel processing of query and language models to generate an original and unique message and make it available to the user.

Conflict between Individual and Collective Interests: How Can Large Language Models Improve the Tourist Experience?

Tourism can be examined from different perspectives. Although these perspectives are different, they follow a common goal. From the tourist's point of view, tourism is an asset for enjoying, gaining experience, and knowing the world. However, from the point of view of the service provider, tourism is a professional business that must be carefully planned to attract more customers through advertising and achieve the highest satisfaction of the highest number of tourists. The goals of customer and provider seem different. The tourist intends to understand the world better. This is not necessarily the intention of the service provider. In fact, service providers are not educational and research institutions that aim to increase the specialized knowledge of their customers. The tourist intends to enjoy the journey. The service provider's desire may not coincide with the travel plan of the tourist.

However, there is a chance to bring the seller and the buyer closer to each other. Service providers can be brought closer to the tastes of customers. It should not be forgotten that customers are not fully satisfied in any of the production and service areas. Even in the best case, a small percentage of manufactured goods or packaged services offered lack quality or are incompatible with the needs and tastes of customers. Therefore, the central idea of this paper focuses on satisfactory services and happy customers.

The diverse approach of the tourist and his/her boundless desire to turn the journey into a unique experience gives us the chance to resolve this conflict. In recent years, the field of information technology has adopted the two concepts of *Personalization* and *Customization* from the field of *Business Administration*. Over the past two decades, we have witnessed the development of databases in which any user or customer can use personalized services. This means that the database developer or publisher has already included some services in the version supplied to a particular organization (for example, a university) that are not available in the version sold to another organization or customer. Therefore, in the first stage, we are faced with a kind of differentiation between versions of a product that is called personalization. In the second stage and within each organization, each user can customize personalized services for their benefit and according to their taste. Personalization is usually seen at the level of the main features of the database, and customization at the level of the user interface or the way the results are sorted according to the user's taste. In any case, database design, development, and

management technology is one of the best examples of product design based on customer taste. This unique experience can be found in the tourism industry as well.

Suppose we have a group of tourists who have traveled together to a tourist destination. In order to get the satisfaction of the largest number of tourists, the company providing tourism services prepares a package that will appeal to most of the travelers. This package is optimized based on experience, trial and error. However, there is always the risk of a passenger in the crowd who does not like the proposed package and expects the travel plan, including its time and place, means of transportation (train or plane), accommodation (hostel or hotel), visit plan (historical buildings, natural phenomena, and artistic and entertaining events), and the meal plan (breakfast, lunch, and dinner enriched by local dishes and foods), to be arranged according to his/her wishes. What is your solution as a coordinator or tour leader?

As a human being, the coordinator has no choice but to solve the problem by prioritizing the collective benefit, negotiating, and dissuading the passenger from his/her personal desires. However, information technology offers problem-solving capacity on another level. Let's return to the concepts of exponential growth and leveling up. At the new level, collective benefit as a basis for negotiation and convincing the tourist are not very important and useful. With the help of generative artificial intelligence, it is possible to adjust the travel plan package not for the group but for individual tourists. Artificial intelligence eliminates the tourist service company as a planner. However, the company can provide another service and continue its business. The schema is as follows: every tourist makes his/her travel plan personally using the mobile application. In fact, the scenario of moving, visiting, and feeding is completely customized. The tourist service company is bound to change the type of business. They need to transform from scenario writer to aggregator. The new task of the company is to collect similar travel scenarios to a common destination and align the material interests of tourists. The company can still play the role of coordinator. However, they are no longer planning the journey. This kind of using generative artificial intelligence changes the role of the company from agent to consular. They will provide advisory services in the field of choosing the route, means of transportation, accommodation, and visiting and feeding plan. It is the tourist who designs, modifies, and finalizes the plan according to his/her own taste. The company collects and optimizes the scenarios of tourists who will travel

to a specific destination in a certain period of time through the connections it has with accommodations, restaurants, local tour guides, and organizers of entertainment programs, and gets a significant discount for the benefit of tourists. The company profit has already been guaranteed.

In this framework, the role of the mobile application equipped with large language models is to pay close attention to the tourist's background and use a recommender system to prescribe a travel scenario to the tourist based on his/her query and the data available in the knowledge repository. Here, users have access to an integrated system that identifies the user based on the first login and then follows his/her entire search behavior in order to find the best and most satisfactory travel scenario. The tourist enters as a user of a meta-information system. After user authentication and determining the access level, a variety of services can be provided. The system can analyze the user's previous search history. The system knows about the different locations that the user has been in over the past years. The system can even guess almost certainly what the user's profession and expertise are and what mood s/he moves from during the week. The system understands the artistic and literary interests of the user. The system is aware of the user's social interactions and professional communications. The system knows how much the user likes to walk and exercise. The system recognizes that the user moves in the city with public transportation or with a private car. The system understands the user's eating habits based on the place and time s/he spends eating, as well as calculating the user's body condition and the number of calories s/he needs. Most importantly, the system has obtained the same information and much more from millions of other users.

LLMs play their unique role here. They have a warehouse full of processed data that has the power to diagnose and prescribe anything from users' academic interests, entertainment habits, political views, and even their private behaviors. It is enough for the supposed tourist to subscribe to the application and submit the query (a travel destination such as Persepolis in Iran, the Triple Pyramids in Egypt, the Rigistan in Samarkand, Uzbekistan, or the Great Wall of China) to the system with a personal login account. The analysis of the user's personal data and the sum of the processed data of thousands of other tourists who have similarities in gender, age, education, language, personality, and occupation with this user results in the preparation of a unique, personalized, and customized travel scenario, which of

course may have overlapped with another person's suggested travel scenario. The assumed user as a tourist is not aware of the similarity of his/her history with other people and the similarity of his/her travel scenario with the travel scenario of others. S/he has his/her own unique scenario, and s/he is happy with it. However, s/he is looking for a way to make travel cheaper. The tourist service provider company logs in with a corporate account and reviews a number of scenarios similar to a common destination at a higher access level, which is provided by the application designer based on the payment of a higher subscription fee and assuming that the private data of users have been protected legally. The same large language model that in phase one supported the user with the data of millions of other tourists, in phase two helps the tourist service provider to design a good reformed scenario that is the closest version to the individual scenario of several tourists. The company's scenario includes most of the elements of the reviewed scenarios, and its advantage is to get discounts for accommodations, restaurants, and art galleries based on the number of tourists. More similar tourists, more similar scenarios. More similar scenarios, more chance to make the most popular scenario. Through the communication channel of the application (an instant messenger, for example), the company can suggest the modified and cheaper scenario to the tourists. It is likely that they will compromise and give up their personal scenario in favor of the revised scenario. This is a service that large language models provide to tourists before starting their journey. Figure 3 illustrates this type of scenario development.

Figure 3-Developing An Inclusive Scenario for Fellow Travelers

Another important service that these models provide to tourists is during the journey. Since, according to the central idea of this paper, the company providing tourist services does not need to accompany the tourists as a planner during the journey and assume legal responsibilities, the travel package can be compiled collectively and implemented individually. In fact, tourists use a similar package without knowing or contacting each other. They may start the journey from the same origin and be present in the same vehicle along the way. However, they have no contact with each other. They will be present in the same residence. However, each of them follows their own travel plan. They will have joint historical, cultural, and recreational visits. However, everyone experiences a personal and separate pleasure. The interesting service of large language models to the tourist is that it recustomizes every part of the journey. For example, in the first step, when the tourist arrives at the train station or the airport, based on his/her history, the mobile application can compare the facilities and limitations of the station or airport to the stations or airports that the user has visited before. It will offer the tourist a better chance to relax in the short time of being in that location. Similar services in the vehicle, in the residence, in historical places, in restaurants, etc. will be offered again based on the user data and the analysis of the common experiences of fellow

travelers. Through adopting this model, the tourist gets out of the limited framework of the company's travel plan, experiences the maximum flexibility and price reduction, and will achieve his/her important goals of enjoying, gaining experience, and knowing the world.

The Future: Technical and Economic Perspectives of Generative AI-Powered Travel Mobile Applications

The author of this paper is very optimistic about the future of the tourism industry. Compared to some other industries, tourism has fewer risk factors and more chance to fully adapt to technology. From a technical point of view, large language models are revolutionizing all academic and business fields. They will give all humans a better chance to be educated, to be employed, to be treated, to have fun, and generally to live a healthy and enjoyable life. The central idea of this paper is to grow the technical capabilities of the tourism industry exponentially. In this paper, it was shown how different components of a meta-information system (a generative AI-powered mobile application) can provide integrated advantages to the user and how the tourist as a user can make the journey a more enjoyable experience. The author believes that the preparation of the requirements of the proposed application is one of the urgent needs of the development of the tourism industry.

From an economic point of view, this idea can help to optimize the cycle of wealth in the tourism industry in a healthier way. In general, any proposal that can improve the processes of this industry and give tourists the chance to travel cheaper, more comfortable, and more enjoyable will improve this industry. The higher the turnover of the tourism industry, the greater its capacity for the attraction of better ideas and customer-friendly products and services.

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